

Online Oral Presentation #21 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Sevgi Cirakli
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7992-1376>

Burak Sariaydin
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-1509-0407>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University Education and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

Ordu University Education and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Neurological development begins intrauterine and peaks at 2 years after birth. The progression of motor development begins with head holding in the 2nd month and continues with supported sitting, unsupported sitting and unsupported walking, which we expect to occur under normal conditions by the 18th month at the latest. Failure or delay in these steps is one of the reasons for consulted to a pediatrician with a clinic for hypotonic infant.

Materials and Methods: Patients referral in the pediatric neurology outpatient clinic with hypotonic infant clinic who were found to have low vitamin B12 levels and we are treated were evaluated.

Results: Four patients seen at the pediatric neurology outpatient clinic with the diagnosis of hypotonic infants and diagnosed with B12 deficiency were included. The patients were found to be deficient in B12. Levels were 100, 120, 130, 130 pg/ml (mean 120 pg/ml). As the patients were breastfed, their mothers were also asked to have blood tests. Two mothers had blood tests and vitamin B12 levels were found to be low. B12 treatment was started in all infants. Sublingual methylcobalamin spray was started because of its ease of use and to prevent neurological complications caused by rapid B12 elevation with intramuscular treatment. As the B12 levels increased in all the infants, their motor development gradually improved according to their age.

Conclusion: Before proceeding to further examinations in children with motor and mental developmental delay, B12 level and supplementation if necessary are very important.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference. Patients referral in the pediatric neurology outpatient clinic with hypotonic infant clinic who were found to have low vitamin B12 levels and we are treated were evaluated. Consent for the study was obtained from the patients' families.

KEYWORDS

B12 deficiency, hypotonic infants

INTRODUCTION

Neurological development begins intrauterine and peaks at 2 years after birth. The progression of motor development begins with head holding in the 2nd month and continues with supported sitting, unsupported sitting and unsupported walking, which we expect to occur under normal conditions by the 18th month at the latest. Failure or delay in these steps is one of the reasons for consulted to a pediatrician with a clinic for hypotonic infant. Vitamin B12 plays a role in the development of central and peripheral nerves. A deficiency of this vitamin, which usually cannot be obtained from external sources due to inadequate nutrition, may lead to hypotonic infant clinic.

CASE PRESENTATION

Four patients seen at the pediatric neurology outpatient clinic with the diagnosis of hypotonic infants and diagnosed with B12 deficiency were included. The patients were 6, 6, 8 and 9 months (mean 7.25 months) old at the time of presentation. Two (50%) of the patients were female and two (50%) were male. Two 6-month-old patients presented with complaint of inability to hold head and 8- and 9-month-old patients presented with complaints of being unable to sit unsupported.

All patients were born at term and had no history of stay in an in the neonatal intensive care unit. There was no parental consanguinity. There was no family history of muscle disease. On physical examination, deep tendon reflexes were present. However, marked hypotonic and difficulty in focusing the eyes were observed depending on the monthly development.

All patients had normal heel blood tests. Routine blood tests including hemogram, biochemistry, thyroid hormones and vitamin D were within normal limits. The patients were found to be deficient in B12. Levels were 100, 120, 130, 130 pg/ml (mean 120 pg/ml). As the patients were breastfed, their mothers were also asked to have blood tests. Two mothers had blood tests and vitamin B12 levels were found to be low.

B12 treatment was started in all infants. Sublingual methylcobalamin spray was started because of its ease of use and to prevent neurological complications caused by rapid B12 elevation with intramuscular treatment. As the B12 levels increased in all the infants, their motor development gradually improved according to their age. At the four-month follow-up, all infants had reached the developmental milestones or their months without any physiotherapy programme.

DISCUSSION

Vitamin B12 is mainly found in animal foods (fish, eggs, milk, meat). Water-soluble vitamin B12 is not produced by the body. Therefore, its level in the body varies with dietary intake (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022). Children with vitamin B12 deficiency can present with a wide variety of clinical symptoms and findings (Rasmussen, Fernhoff, & Scanlon, 2001). They often present with non-specific findings such as weakness, fatigue, growth retardation and restlessness. In addition, hematological and neurological findings may be present (Ohls & Christensen, 2004). Neurological symptoms may precede hematological changes and may even be seen in the absence of hematological findings (Means & Fairfield, 2022). If the deficiency is not detected at an early age, it may cause neurodevelopmental retardation in the child compared with his or her peers. Therefore, detection and treatment of deficiency is of great importance in pediatric health care (Demir et al., 2013). Neurological findings related to vitamin B12 deficiency can improve within days with the initiation of appropriate treatment (Dror & Allen, 2008). In our patients, neurological development caught up with their peers within 4 months with treatment of B12 deficiency.

Before proceeding to further examinations in children with motor and mental developmental delay, B12 level and supplementation if necessary are very important.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Demir, N., Koc, A., Üstyol, L., Peker, E., & Abuhandan, M. (2013). Clinical and neurological findings of severe vitamin B12 deficiency in infancy and importance of early diagnosis and treatment. *Journal of Paediatrics and Child Health*, 49(10), 820–824.

Dror, D. K., & Allen, L. H. (2008). Effect of vitamin B12 deficiency on neurodevelopment in infants: Current knowledge and possible mechanisms. *Nutrition Reviews*, 66(5), 250–255.

Means, R. T., & Fairfield, K. M. (2022). Causes and pathophysiology of vitamin B12 and folate deficiencies. In J. S. Tirnauer (Ed.), *UpToDate*. UpToDate, Waltham, MA. (Erişim: 01 Eylül 2022).

Ohls, R. K., & Christensen, R. D. (2004). Megaloblastic anemias. In R. E. Behrman, R. M. Kliegman & H. B. Jenson (Eds.), *Nelson textbook of pediatrics* (17th ed., pp. 1611–1613). Elsevier Science.

Rasmussen, S. A., Fernhoff, P. M., & Scanlon, K. S. (2001). Vitamin B12 deficiency in children and adolescents. *Journal of Pediatrics*, 138(1), 10–17.

World Health Organization. (2022). *Vitamin B12: Fact sheet for health professionals*.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Sevgi Cirakli

Ordu University Education and Research Hospital

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7992-1376>

sevgigumusoglu@hotmail.com